

MAIN CHARACTERISTICS OF PHRASEOLOGISMS IN ENGLISH

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ANNOTATION

The main focus of phraseology as a branch of linguistics focuses on studying phraseology. Phraseologism - two or more semantically interrelated phrase composed of words. Phraseologism is a lexical unit like a word. They are ready in the language like words. The study of phraseology, stages of formation and their main features will be analyzed in this article.

Keywords: phraseological units, phraseology, idioms, phraseologism, lexical units.

INTRODUCTION

According to their external form classification of various features of phraseological expressions can also be determined. The most important in this classification is the number of words in the content. To the result of classification, to the nature of expressions it is possible to determine how many words it consists of. Many linguists say that phraseological expressions are only more than two words.

But observations show that there are two, three and more phraseological phrases consists of words. But some linguists stand for that there are some expressions consisting of one word too.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Idiomatic words consist of only single words and have an idiomatic meaning. But the phrase cannot reflect the characteristics that it expresses.

One of the most popular linguists V.V.Vinogradov divided phraseological units into 3 main classes in his scientific works.

1. Phraseological confusions
2. Phraseological compounds

3. Phraseological associations

The first group of phraseologies is the units in which the meanings of the components are not related to the meanings of the whole units. For instance,

Heavy father-главный роль в театре

Red tape- бюрократия

Phraseological confusion is a completely different meaning of a phrase. However, unlike phraseological compounds, their meanings are not understood from the meanings of the constituent parts.

Based on metaphor, the meaning is clear and unambiguous. The lexical components of phraseological compounds are the most stable expressions. For instance,

- | | |
|------------------------------------|--|
| -to look a gift horse in the mouth | (to examine a person too critically. To find fault with smth one gained without effort); |
| -to ride the hide horse | (to behave in a superior, haughtily, over bearing way); |

Due to the complexity and multifaceted nature of the phraseological material, in recent years it has been studied using a variety of methods and techniques. Its typical representatives are the leading scientists Charles Balli and A.V. Kunin.

The study of phraseology, the study of this field, led to its formation as an independent linguistic field. He enriched the science of linguistics theoretically and practically. However, it should not be concluded that there are no unexplored problems in the field of phraseology. The term phraseology also served to express different meanings in Turkic studies.

Mirza Karimbek, a 19th-century Turkic scholar, followed the traditions of the time and used the word "phrase" in the meaning of "sentence" in his work, as in other figurative grammars written in Russian. When he says phraseological compound, he means large linguistic units from words.

Azerbaijan linguists B.Chponzoda and F.Ogazoda, in their work "Grammar of the Turkish language", thinking about the sections of linguistics, along with the terms "Semasiology", "Stylistics" were widely used in linguistics at that time. Used the word "idiocy" against the term "idiomatism." Phraseology is one of the youngest branches of Turkic studies, as its systematic study, the study of semantic and grammatical features, functional features of phraseological units began in the 40s and 50s of the twentieth century. Given that phraseological units are functionally close to words, some linguists have considered them to be lexical words, combinations, or lexical units, and have included them in the study of syntax or construction.

As in Russian linguistics, the field of phraseology in Turkic studies continues to be understood in a narrow and broad sense. Phraseologisms in the broadest sense include all fixed combinations (proverbs, sayings, and idiomatic combinations), their no idiomatic fixed phraseological groups, and pairs of words. Their common denominator is stability and language readiness.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The comparative characteristic of phraseological units also has a quantitative aspect – the number of equivalents in a particular phraseological unit, their comparative use. Aspect correlation of phraseological units, i.e. the correlation of their component composition and grammatical organization, for English and languages, has only an indirect, structural and semantic character, since for unrelated languages, the direct material identity of lexical components and grammatical structures is not typical. The functional-semantic correlation of phraseological units of different languages means, ideally, the identity of a lot of composition and additional connotations in the aggregate content of the compared phraseological units.

The combination of aspect and functional-semantic identity gives full interlingual phraseological equivalents. For example: „p heart of stone . tosh yurak. If only an abstract figurative model unites phraseological units in the languages under consideration, then their aggregate functional-semantic correlation loses its character, since according to such an abstract model, a number of phraseological units with a similar meaning can be formed. When only the abstract figurative model coincides, the functional-semantic correlation of phraseological units is usually incomplete. Interlanguage aspect correlation of phraseological units and their functional-semantic correlation are not directly dependent on each other. Their relationship is subject to the general provision on the asymmetry of the signifying and signified linguistic sign.

Differences in the aggregate phraseological meaning with the aspect identity of the compared phraseological units of the English and Uzbek languages may be the result of multidirectional rethinking. Another reason may be the appearance of additional semantic shades against the background of an identical common meaning. For example: positively colored English phraseological unit keep one's chin up (do not hang your nose, keep a stiff upper lip) can be translated into Uzbek to turn up your nose, which carries a negative connotation (to assume importance, to behave arrogantly). The presence or absence of structural and semantic equivalents in the compared languages can be predicted by some characteristics of the phraseological units of the source language themselves. These characteristics relate to the component composition, syntactic structure, semantic and formal mechanism-phraseological and cumulative stylistic properties of phraseological units.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the task of the translator is to understand the meaning of the source text and express the same meaning (more precisely, the system of values) by means of a different language. In this case, an interlanguage transformation occurs, i.e., the replacement of one sign system with another, which leads to inevitable semantic losses. The translator must keep them to a minimum, i.e. ensure a greater degree of equivalence between the source text and the translation text, which is impossible without performing various translation transformations.

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